

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE PRESENTATION OF NEW EDUCATIONAL MATERIAL IN PHYSICS CLASSES

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Abstract. This article discusses the role of using interactive methods in physics lessons. Interactive learning is, first of all, dialogue learning, during which interaction between the teacher and the student takes place.

Keywords: interactive teaching methods, intensify the learning process.

INTRODUCTION

Today it has become obvious that it is not the individual who needs to be managed, but the process of its development. And this means that priority in the work of a teacher is given to methods of indirect pedagogical influence: there is a rejection of frontal methods, slogans and appeals, abstaining from excessive didacticism and edification; instead, dialogical methods of communication, a joint search for truth, development through the creation of educational situations, and a variety of creative activities are highlighted.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main methodological innovations today are associated with the use of interactive teaching methods. The word “interactive” came to us from the English word “interact”. “Inter” is “mutual”, “act” is to act.

Interactive means the ability to interact or is in a conversation, dialogue mode with someone (a person) or something (for example, a computer). Consequently, interactive learning is, first of all, dialogue learning, during which interaction between the teacher and the student takes place. The learning process is carried out in conditions of constant, active interaction of all students.

Interactive learning methods include those that promote involvement in the active process of acquiring and processing knowledge.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interactive learning methods: brainstorming (attack), group work, checklist or test, role-playing game, game exercises, project development, solving situational problems, expert group discussion, playing out situations, discussion of plot drawings, survey-Quiz (control) and etc.

First of all, interactive methods:

- awaken students’ interest;
- encourage the active participation of everyone in the educational process;
- appeal to the feelings of each student;

- promote effective learning of educational material;
- have a multifaceted impact on students;
- provide feedback (audience response);
- form opinions and attitudes among students;
- form life skills;
- promote behavior change.

V.A. Sukhomlinsky said that the best teacher is the one who forgets that he is a teacher [1]. As soon as the teacher drops the mentoring tone, shows genuine interest, forgets that he is “at the top” and “stands next to him,” the students will respond and show sincere interest in communication.

There are a huge number of interactive learning methods. Each teacher can independently come up with new forms of working with the class.

I would call interactive teaching methods active, because... they make it possible to intensify the educational process, create a favorable emotional mood that promotes the development of cognitive interest in the subject, students' creative abilities, and independent work skills.

During lessons I use the following CDs: “Open Physics”, “Living Physics”, “Tutor. Physics”.

In "Living Physics" you can easily and quickly create experimental schemes, models of physical objects, and force fields. After completing the work, you can immediately get the result in the form of animation, graph, table, chart. The program allows you to bring to life experiments and illustrations for physics course problems, helps students better understand the theory, solve the problem, and comprehend the laboratory work.

Students have the opportunity to understand the nature of the object itself, to actively participate in the process of cognition of it, independently changing both its parameters and operating conditions. The use of interactive teaching methods can not only have a positive impact on students' understanding of the structure and essence of the functioning of an object, but, more importantly, on their mental development.

I examined the use of a computer for compiling tests, modeling physical processes and phenomena, computerizing physical experiments, solving problems and carrying out quantitative calculations, developing computer-based algorithms and action programs for students, carrying out self-control and standardizing knowledge control.

As a result of the use of interactive teaching methods, the learning process is individualized. Each student learns the material according to his own plan, in

accordance with his individual perception abilities. As a result of such training, after just 1-2 lessons, students will be at different stages of learning new material. This will lead to the fact that the teacher will not be able to continue teaching students using the traditional classroom-lesson system. The main objective of this type of training is to ensure that students are at the same stage before learning new material and at the same time they have all the allotted work time occupied.

CONCLUSION

In my work I use interactive teaching methods. This is not only the use of a computer lesson model, but the use of all available means: books, teaching aids and teaching aids.

When planning lessons, it is necessary to find the optimal combination of such programs with other teaching tools.

The use of interactive methods ensures: high motivation, strength of knowledge, creativity and imagination, sociability, active life position, team spirit, the value of individuality, freedom of expression, emphasis on activity, mutual respect, democracy.

References:

1. Sukhomlinsky V.A. Wise power of the collective. Moscow: Young Guard, 2015. P. 238.
2. Krainova E.E. Development of creative nodes of students in physics lessons Kazan, Young scientist No. 2 (188) January 2018.
3. Utemov V. V., Zinovkina M. M., Gorev P. M. Creative pedagogy: Practical course of scientific creativity: Darslik. – Kirov: ANOO "Interregional CITO
4. Bukhvalov V. A. Development of students in the creative and collaborative process.-M.:2018
5. G.I.Yuldasheva. (2023). Methods of Developing Intellectual Skills of Students in Physics Lessons. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development. 2(6), 561-564
6. G.I.Yuldasheva. (2023). Применение инновационных технологий в обучении физике. Международный научный журнал «Научный импульс». № 9 (100). 63-67
7. А. М.Мирзакулов., Г. И. Йулдашева. (2022). Физика дарсларида ўқувчиларни илмий тадқиқот таълимга йўналтириш билан уларнинг интеллектуал салоҳиятларини ривожлантириш омиллари. NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi. 7-son. 44-50

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8. A. M.Мирзақулов., Г.И.Йулдашева. (2022). Физика фанини ўқитишда мақсадни шакллантириш асослари. Scientific progress. Volume 3(5). 140-144.
9. G.I.Yuldasheva. (2021). On the creation of virtual laboratories (in physics) and their application in the field of education. Международная конференция академических наук. 29-31.
10. G.I.Yuldasheva. (2022). Maktabda fizika darslari samaradorligini oshirishda virtual laboratoriyalarning o'рни. NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi. №11. 513-519
11. Ibragimovna, Y. G., & Xokimovna, K. Z. (2022). The use of pedagogical software, that is, virtual laboratories, in the teaching of physics. Current research journal of pedagogics, 3(05), 15-18.
12. Йулдашева, Г. И. (2021). Физика фанини педагогик дастурий воситалар асосида ўқитишда интеллект ривожланиши соҳасидаги илмий тадқиқотлар. Ф.: ФДУ.
13. Yuldasheva, G. (2023). Ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari. 1-qism. F.: FDU.
14. Yuldasheva, G., & Shermatova, H. (2022). Ta'limda innovatsion texnologiyalarning qo'llanilish istiqbollari. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 5-9.